

**Microdetermination of some Phenols using
Bromine Chloride**

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STANDARD solutions of interhalogen compounds ICl , IBr , ICl_3 and BrCl have been extensively used as analytical reagents¹. It has been established that the bromination by BrCl takes place with rapidity as compared to the conventional bromate-bromide mixture. The inherent usefulness of BrCl for the quantitative determination of several organic compounds² led to the investigation of its applicability to a few more phenolic compounds, viz., phloroglucinol, thymol, pyrogallol and 2,4-dinitrophenol. The method offers the advantages of rapidity, simplicity, sensitivity and reproducibility.

Experimental

A stock solution of sodium thiosulphate (12.416 g in 1 dm³ of distilled water) was prepared and

standardised using standard potassium dichromate iodometrically. Bromine chloride was prepared by dissolving potassium bromide (1.9835 g) and potassium bromate (1.3917 g) in distilled water (125 ml) cooled in ice, concentrated HCl (100 ml) was then added and the solution was made upto 500 ml. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was first determined by dissolving the sample (2–10 mg) in glacial acetic acid-water and allowing it to react with known excess of bromine chloride solution for about 20–30 min in an ice-bath. The excess reagent was back-titrated against hypo iodometrically. To an aliquot containing 2–10 mg of the sample was added glacial acetic acid (5 ml) followed by bromine chloride solution (5 ml) and the reaction mixture after shaking well was cooled in an ice-bath for ~0.5 h. Potassium iodide solution (15%; 5 ml) was then added, allowed to stand for 5 min with gentle shaking and titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was examined. The results reveal that phloroglucinol requires 3 mol of BrCl, pyrogallol 2 mol whereas thymol and 2,4-dinitrophenol require 1 mol each of BrCl. The results of the microdetermination of some phenols are summarised in Table 1.

The results show that they are precise and the maximum deviation is about 0.68. Since the reactivity of BrCl is known to be higher in polar solvents, acetic acid was used as the medium. The results improved when the estimations were carried out at low temperatures.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PHENOLS

Phenols	Weight taken mg	Weight found mg	Standard deviation*	Relative error %
Phloroglucinol	2.08–10.4	2.02–10.38	0.32	2.05
Thymol	2.11–10.55	2.14–10.51	0.41	1.65
Pyrogallol	2.01–8.00	1.96–8.06	0.63	2.32
2,4-Dinitrophenol	2.03–6.13	1.99–6.08	0.68	2.18

* Five determinations in each case.

The reported method has the advantage that the estimations could be carried out with rapidity using only one standard solution employing similar experimental conditions for all the compounds studied. The microdetermination of cresols showed large % deviation.

References

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